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An Investigation into Academic Self-efficacy, Peer Influence and Examination Anxiety as Correlates of Academic Achievement Drive of Library and Information Science Students

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Abstract

In any institution of learning, the true prove of any student's performance is the level of academic achievement grade which may be a product of many independent variables. On the other hand, an impaired academic achievement motivation more often than not may portend danger on the learning outcome and intellectual well being of such student(s). This study therefore investigated the relationship between academic self-efficacy, peer group and examination anxiety with academic achievement drive of library and information science students. The study used descriptive survey research design and guided by three research questions as well as three formulated and tested hypothesis. Data were collected through four validated instruments from 399 library and information science students randomly selected from universities in Nigeria. Data collected were analyzed using Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at $P>0.05$ level of significance. The outcome of the study revealed that the independent variables (academic self-efficacy, peer influence and examination anxiety) have statistical significant influence on academic achievement drive of library and information science students. To this end, it was recommended among other things, that students should believe in their ability to excel, should as a matter of necessity take their studies seriously, form good study habit and set for themselves SMART goals that can spur them into developing positive academic achievement drive for academic excellence.

Keywords: Academic Self-efficacy, Peer Influence, Examination Anxiety, Academic Achievement, Library and Information Science Students.

1.0. Introduction

In any institution of learning, the true prove of any student's performance is the level of academic achievement grade which may be a product of many independent variables. On the other hand, an impaired academic achievement motivation more often than not may portend danger on the learning outcome and intellectual well being of such student(s). Academic achievement represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, and university (Steinmayr; Meißner; Weidinger & Wirthwein, 2015), while expressed academic achievement drive is the tendency to endeavor for success and to choose goal oriented success activities. Besides the relevance for an individual, academic achievement is of utmost importance for the wealth of a nation and its prosperity. The strong association between a society's level of academic achievement and positive socioeconomic development is one reason for conducting international test on academic achievement, such as PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment), administered by the OECD (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development). The results of these studies provide information about different indicators of a nation's academic achievement. Such information is used to analyze the strengths and weaknesses of a nation's educational system and to guide educational policy decisions. Given the individual and societal importance of academic achievement, it is not surprising that academic achievement is the research focus of many scientists. Be it as it may, academic achievement desire is an interactive construct representing the direction a learner is going, the emotional energy and affective experience supporting or inhibiting movement in that direction and the expectancies that learners have about reaching their destination or achieving their academic goals. Students with high level of academic achievement drive exhibit certain characteristic as they are usually motivated during teaching and learning interactive process to expand greater mental effort in organizing rehearsing information, monitoring level of understanding and relating new material to prior knowledge (Okoiye, 2011).

The highlighted patterned academic characteristic disposition is believed to depend heavily on interplay of the students' full commitment as a result of academic self-efficacy which is seen as the students' beliefs and attitudes toward their capabilities to achieve academic success, as well

as belief in their ability to fulfill academic tasks and the successful learning of the materials (Bandura, 1997; Schunk & Ertmer, 2000) and the functioning of the social personal and personality constructs which serve as barrier to academic attainment in school. In this angle, factors like peer influence which according to The University of Melbourne (n.d.) is when one chooses to do something he wouldn't otherwise do, because he wants to feel accepted and valued by friends and examination anxiety described by Zeidner (1998), as is a combination of physiological over-arousal, tension and somatic symptoms, along with worry, dread, fear of failure, and catastrophe, that occur before or during test situations come to mind. It is to find answers to this puzzle that this study of investigating the relationship between academic self-efficacy, peer influence and examination anxiety with academic achievement drive was embarked upon.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Over the years, researchers, stakeholders and behavioral scientists have observed that some students have this intense desire to excel academically while some exhibit this lackadaisical attitude towards their academic achievement. This development has gotten to a point of concern that has enunciated discussions and debates to not only among Educational and Counseling Psychology but also among educationists, parents, lecturers and even librarians. The preoccupation of all is, how to enhance the academic desire of learners in schools which library and information science students form part and their research efforts noted Goetz, Reinhard, Nathan & Ludwig (2006) and Okoiye (2011), have always been diversified in this regard. This phenomenon as perceived by stakeholders is a wind that blows no good to the society at large as it is believed that fostering students' academic achievement drive in education would impact positively on their intellectual ability and academic attainment considered as imperative aspect of effective learning as the degree of any student's reaction to education is a determinant of how far he or she can achieve academically. However despite the ample research in motivation antecedent, the impact of individual student learner differences has often been neglected (Pintrich, 2003). This is particularly surprising as the need for a more personal pedagogical approach grows with increasing diversity of the student population (Friga, Bettis & Sullivan, 2003) and the enhanced focus on student-centered and life-long learning experience (Evans &

Cools, 2011). Furthermore, lack of academic achievement motivation is one of the most critical factors affecting learning especially among the disadvantaged learners and the challenge of educators has always been how to stimulate and enhance the motivation of these students whose enthusiasm for learning is in doubt. Besides, most studies relating to the topic were secondary schools based thus no serious work to the best of knowledge of the researcher has been carried out on students of higher institutions in this part of the globe let alone on library and information science students

It is against this backdrop and to bridge the gap created in knowledge as it relates to institutions of higher learning and library and information science students in particular that this study was embarked upon as to investigating the relationship that exist between academic self-efficacy, peer influence and examination anxiety with academic achievement drive (also known as motivation) of library and information science students in Nigerian universities.

1.3. Research Objectives

Specifically, the principle objective of this study was to investigate the relationship between academic self-efficacy, peer influence and examination anxiety with academic achievement drive of library and information science students. Other objectives include:

- i. To establish the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement motivation of library and information science student.
- ii. To ascertain the correlation between peer influence and academic achievement drive of library and information students.
- iii. To ascertain the relationship between examination anxiety and academic achievement drive of library and information science students.

1.4. Research Questions

The study was guided by the three under listed research question

- i. What is the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement motivation of library and information science students?
- ii. What is the correlation between peer influence and academic achievement drive of library and information students?

- iii. What is the relationship between examination anxiety and academic achievement drive of library and information science students?

1.5. Hypotheses

H01: There is no statistical significant relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic achievement motivation of library and information science students

H02: There is no statistical significant relationship between peer influence and academic achievement drive of library and information science students.

H03: There is no statistical significant relationship between examination anxiety and academic achievement drive of library and information science students.

2.0. Literature review

2.1. Conceptual Framework

2.1.1. Academic Self-efficacy

Academic self-efficacy refers to the beliefs about one's capabilities to learn or perform behaviors at designed levels (Bandura, 1997), and is said to have a measure of control over individual's thoughts, feelings and actions. Self-efficacy is also a much stronger predictor of how effectively people will perform a given task than either their self confidence or their self-esteem. A high degree of self-efficacy leads people to work hard and persist in the face of setbacks (Bandura, 1982). Academic self-efficacy therefore is one of the important factors influencing academic performance. Academic self-efficacy refers to the students' beliefs and attitudes toward their capabilities to achieve academic success, as well as belief in their ability to fulfill academic tasks and the successful learning of the materials (Meinhardt & Pekrun, 2003 and Chin, Williams, Taylor & Harvey, 2017).. Academic self-efficacy beliefs therefore lead to the individuals' excellent performance through increasing commitment, endeavor and perseverance (Pintrich, 2003)

2.1.2. Examination Anxiety

Almost everyone will feel nervous or experience some level of anxiety when faced with an examination, assessment, or performance situation. In other words, the period of examination is

considered an extremely anxious time. Anxiety can cause medical problems or reduce the efficiency of examination performance. Of course, most people have some anxiety reaction to examinations. Examination anxiety is a combination of physiological over-arousal, tension and somatic symptoms, along with worry, dread, fear of failure, and catastrophizing, that occur before or during test situations (Khizar, Anwar & Khanum, 2015). Suffice it to say, that examination anxiety is a common and natural response for many students in the preparation before, and during examinations. In fact, a moderate level of anxiety or stress is crucial to performing well – this helps us to be psychologically and physically alert in an exam or assessment situation. The period of examination is considered an extremely anxious time. Anxiety can cause medical problems or reduce the efficiency of exam performance (The University of Melbourne, n.d.)

According to Phillips, Martin, and Myers (1972) anxiety is reaction of different environmental factors and emotionality and cognition are two basic sub components of test anxiety. Cognitive component causes worry which reduces attention, concentration and information processing process while emotionality is related to physical symptoms or physical reactions as horror of examination. Researches supported that cognitive element was more contributing factor of lower academic achievement among adolescent (Bandlos, Yates, & Thorndike-Christ, 1995; Williams, 1991; Humbree, 1988; Lufie, 2004; Mathews, Zeidner & Roberts, 2006; Bembenutty, 2009; Unruh and Lowe, 2010). Examinations are tools to evaluate students knowledge, skills and attitude and achievement is struggle for success and avoidance from failure. (Covington, 2004; Heafner ,2004). However along with many other factors examination anxiety is consider as a major factor that effect student's achievement in different countries (Sarason,1984; Zollar & Ben-chain, 1990; Spielberger, 1980). Examination anxiety is the set of phenomenological, psychological, and behavioral responses that effect student's achievement both positively and negatively.

The University of Melbourne (n.d.), highlighted some of the causes of examination anxiety to include:

- ❖ Negative past experiences of examinations

- ❖ Lack of adequate preparation, or knowledge of examination-taking techniques or study methods
- ❖ Unhelpful thinking about the examination situation (e.g., “I’m going to lose control!”), yourself (e.g., “I can’t do this.”), and/or outcome (e.g., “I’m going to fail.”)
- ❖ Excessive pressure to achieve and/or perfectionism
- ❖ Strong fear of failure
- ❖ Poor self-care, including insufficient sleep, unhealthy eating, lack of exercise or relaxation.

2.1.3. Academic Achievement

Academic achievement is the amount of knowledge derived from learning by the learner.

The learner gains knowledge from instructions he or she receives at school which is organized around a set of core activities in which a teacher assigns tasks to students and evaluates and compares the quality of their work. The school thus provides a wide variety of achievement experiences than does the family (Tucker, 2008; Zayco, 2002; & Sullivan, 2009). Therefore, academic achievement should be considered to be a multifaceted construct that comprises different domains of learning. Because the field of academic achievement is very wide ranging and covers a broad variety of educational outcomes, the definition of academic achievement depends on the indicators used to measure it. Among the many criteria that indicate academic achievement, there are very general indicators such as procedural and declarative knowledge acquired in an educational system, more curricular based criteria such as grades or performance on an educational achievement test, and cumulative indicators of academic achievement such as educational degrees and certificates. All criteria have in common that they represent intellectual endeavors and thus, more or less, mirror the intellectual capacity of a person. Akomolafe (2010), academic achievement is based on several factors, such as the student’s attitude, interest, personal characteristics, motivation and social class which in addition to learning are known to influence their academic achievement.

In developed societies, academic achievement plays an important role in every person’s life. Academic achievement as measured by the GPA (grade point average) or by standardized

assessments designed for selection purpose such as the SAT (Scholastic Assessment Test) determines whether a student will have the opportunity to continue his or her education. Therefore, academic achievement defines whether one can take part in higher education, and based on the educational degrees one attains, influences one's vocational career after education. Academic achievement so to speak, represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, and university. School systems mostly define cognitive goals that either apply across multiple subject areas (Steinmayr, Meißner, Weidinger, & Wirthwein, 2015)

Academic Achievement in general, refers to the degree or level of success or proficiency, attained in some specific area, concerning scholastic or academic work. Academic or Educational age, accomplishment quotient or achievement quotients are the most commonly used means to interpret the level of Academic Achievement of pupils in a specific given subject matter (Bhat & Bhardwaj, 2014). In other words, academic achievement is specified level of attainment or proficiency in academic work as evaluated by the teachers, by standardized tests or behavior or by a combination of both. Academic Achievement or Academic Performance of students therefore is an aspect of their total behaviour. It is the product of the interaction of the student, as an individual with his environment, namely school, teachers and peers.

2.1.4. Academic Achievement Drive (Motivation)

The attitude that is often used in conjunction with academic achievement is achievement motivation or drive. Achievement motivation can best be understood by examining the meanings of "achievement" and "motivation" separately. Achievement typically stress the importance of accomplishment and attainment with effort involved (Mandel & Marcus 2005). Academic achievement drive is defined as internal condition that stimulates, direct and maintains behaviour and the belief is that there is a strong relationship between learning and motivation (Awan et al., 2011). Van Nuland Dusseldorp, Martens and Boekaerts (2010) see it as an activator or energizer of goal oriented behavior while to Okoiye (2011), academic achievement drive or motivation is an interactive construct representing the direction a learner is going, the emotional energy and affective experience supporting or inhibiting movement in that direction and the expectancies that learners have about reaching their destination or achieving their

academic goals. Suffice it to say, that academic achievement drive is a force which spurs a students into full commitment to realizing the set academic goals and achieving the academic expectancies.

Achievement motivation is further defined as the need to perform well or the striving for success and evidence by persistence and effort in the face of difficulties, achievement motivation is regarded as a central human motivation. Achievement Motivation in the school context can be defined as a driving force that accounts for students' behaviour in achievement situations. It determines cognitive, emotional, and behavioral aspects of students' attachment and contribution to the process of education in the educational subsector (Tucker, Zayco, & Herman, 2002).

Motivation is generally regarded as the drive to achieve targets and the process to maintain the drive. Motivation provides an important foundation to complete cognitive behaviour, such as planning, organization, decision-making, learning, and assessments (Tucker, 2008; Zayco, & Herman, 2002) defined achievement motivation as task-oriented behavior. Academic achievements of individuals are often compared against standards or with others for assessments. The differing perspectives of scholars result in various definitions of achievement motivation. The original definition of achievement motivation was from Atkinson and Feather (1964), who defined it as the comparison of performances with others and against certain standard activities. Atkinson and Feather (1964) suggested that achievement motivation is a combination of two personality variables; tendency to approach success and tendency to avoid failure. (Muola, 2010) defined achievement motivation as the drive to work with diligence and vitality, to constantly steer toward targets, to obtain dominance in challenging a difficult tasks and create sense of achievement as a result. Klose (2008) defined achievement motivation as those factors that affect student's perceptions of their relationship to the achievement setting (e.g. the classroom).

2.2. Empirical and Theoretical Framework

In the last decades, research has univocally proven the importance of academic achievement drive on the learning experience and outcome of students. As noted, motivated students tend to have a better learning process and outcome (Lepper, Corpus & iyenaar, 2005), higher esteem, more creative (Eisenberger & Shanock, 2003), improved psychological well-being (Ryan & Deci, 2000) and more self-regulated. Many authors also believe that academic achievement drive

contributes to the successful academic performance of students (Gottfried, Marcoulides, Gottfried, Oliver & Guerin, 2007). Pintrich and Schunk (2002) regard academic motivation as an integral part of learning while Awan, Noureen and Naz (2011) are of the opinion that lack of academic achievement drive is a big hurdle in learning and a pertinent cause in the deterioration of student' s academic attainment

The exploration of academic achievement has led to numerous empirical studies and fundamental progress such as the development of the first intelligence test by Binet and Simon. Introductory textbooks such as Woolfolk (2007) provide theoretical and empirical insight into the determinants of academic achievement and its assessment. However, as academic achievement is a broad topic, several textbooks have focused mainly on selected aspects of academic achievement, such as enhancing academic achievement or specific predictors of academic achievement. A thorough, short, and informative overview of academic achievement is provided in Spinath (2012). Spinath (2012) emphasizes the importance of academic achievement with regard to different perspectives (such as for individuals and societies, as well as psychological and educational research). Walberg 1986 is an early synthesis of existing research on the educational effects of the time but it still influences current research such as investigations of predictors of academic achievement in some of the large scale academic achievement assessment studies (e.g., Programme for International Student Assessment, PISA). Walberg 1986 highlights the relevance of research syntheses (such as reviews and meta-analyses) as an initial point for the improvement of educational processes. A current work, Hattie 2009, provides an overview of the empirical findings on academic achievement by distinguishing between individual, home, and scholastic determinants of academic achievement according to theoretical assumptions. However, Spinath (2012) points out that it is more appropriate to speak of “predictors” instead of determinants of academic achievement because the mostly cross sectional nature of the underlying research does not allow causal conclusions to be drawn. Large scale scholastic achievement assessments such as PISA (see OECD, 2010) provide an overview of the current state of research on academic achievement, as these studies have investigated established predictors of academic achievement on an international level. Furthermore, these studies, for the first time, have enabled nations to compare their educational systems with other nations and to evaluate them on this basis. However, it should be mentioned critically that this approach may, to

some degree, overestimate the practical significance of differences between the countries. Moreover, the studies have increased the amount of attention paid to the role of family background and the educational system in the development of individual performance. The quality of teaching, in particular, has been emphasized as a predictor of student achievement. Altogether, there are valuable cross sectional studies investigating many predictors of academic achievement. A further focus in educational research has been placed on tertiary educational research. Richardson, et al. (2012) subsumes the individual correlates of university students' performance.

As noted by Bandura (1997) and Schunk & Ertmer, (2000), academic self-efficacy is one of the important factors influencing academic performance. Academic self-efficacy refers to the students' beliefs and attitudes toward their capabilities to achieve academic success, as well as belief in their ability to fulfill academic tasks and the successful learning of the materials. Self-efficacy beliefs lead to the individuals' excellent performance through increasing commitment, endeavor, and perseverance (Pintrich, 2003). The learners with high levels of self-efficacy attribute their failures to lower attempts rather than lower ability, while those with low self-efficacy attribute their failure to their low abilities (Kurbanoglu & Akim, 1977). Therefore, self-efficacy can influence the choice of tasks and perseverance while doing them. In other words, students with low self-efficacy are more likely to be afraid of doing their tasks, avoiding, postponing, and give them up soon (Bandura 1997; Schunk & Ertmer, 2000).

Adeyemo (2007), affirmed that the sources of information from which students appraise their academic self-efficacy beliefs are performance accomplishment, their vicarious experience, and persuasion they get from others and their psychological arousal. He further argued that when students have strong beliefs in their capabilities to undertake academic tasks, they set comparable goal and necessary machinery in motion for actualizing their goals.. Indeed, studies on perceived academic self-efficacy and student learning have confirmed that perceived academic self-efficacy impacts on students' aspiration, level of interest in academic pursuit, academic accomplishment and how well they prepare themselves for different occupational career (Bandura, 1995; Adeyemo, 2007). Bandura (1986) proposed that individuals' efficacy expectations, or their beliefs that they can accomplish a given task or activity, are the major determinant of activity choice, willingness to expend effort, and persistence

In contrast, those with high levels of self-efficacy are more likely to rely on themselves when faced with complex issues to find a solution to the problem, as well as being patient during the process, making more efforts, and persisting longer to overcome the challenges (Sadi & Uyar, 2013; Schunk & Ertmer, 2000; Bandura, 1977). Therefore, it seems that self-efficacy is one of the most important factors in the students' academic success.

For example, Chemers and Garcia (2001) found that the students' self-efficacy in the first year of university is a strong predictor of their future performance. Alyami et al. (2017) conducted a study on 214 university students and revealed that academic self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on their academic performance. Other studies have shown that academic self-efficacy has a considerable effect on the students' learning, motivation, and academic performance (Sadi & Uyar, 2013; Villavicencio & Bernardo, 2013; Ferla, Valcke & Cai 2009), Putwain, Sander & Larkin, 2013). Doménech-Betoret, Abellán-Roselló & Gómez-Artiga (2017).

Ahmad and Safaria (2013) in their study discovered that student with high self efficacy contribute to higher goal than student with low self-efficacy. Students with high self-efficacy believe that they can achieve higher grade on a test of subtraction as compared to research students with low self-efficacy. In other words, students with high self-efficacy believe to solve a greater number of mathematical problems. The other finding suggested that students with high self-efficacy will prefer complex courses than research participants with low self-efficacy. In other words, subjects with high self-efficacy will choose difficult courses of studies in the future. Studies explicated that examination anxiety has impact on university level students and results showed that high achievers had less examination anxiety. Literature support effect of examination anxiety and teachers evaluation practice on student's academic achievement. High anxiety reduces level of motivation and academic achievement (Hancock, 2001; Khalid and Hasan, 2009). A positive level of anxiety can improve students' learning ability and enhance academic achievement of students because this makes students efficient and striving. Low and moderate level of anxiety has positive impact on student's achievement .When this level exceeds and persists for long time then cause failure and low performance (Chapell, Blanding, Takahashi, Silverstein, Newman, Gubi, & McCann, 2005; Onwayed,2005 ; Heather & April, 2009)

Hayat, Shateri, Amini and Shokrpour (2020) who in their findings demonstrated the influence of academic self-efficacy on positive emotions based on Pekrun's control-value theory (Pekrun, 2006.; Pekrun & Stephens, (2010)], revealed that cognitive assessment is supposed to be one of the significant antecedents of academic emotions categorized into control assessments (perceived control) and value assessments (perceived value). Control assessments are related to the individuals' perception of the controllability of achievement activities and their consequences. These assessments are shown through our expectations and perception of competence, such as self-efficacy. Therefore, academic self-efficacy (as a cognitive assessment) can influence academic emotions (Pekrun & Stephens, 2010). It can be expected that, when the students believe in their ability to perform their tasks successfully, they will enjoy the learning process more; also, it seems reasonable that these individuals experience more feelings like hope and pride compared to the students with low self-efficacy. Onwubiko (2022), in a study on the effect of self-efficacy, reading culture, utilization of library habits on the academic achievements of student-librarians discovered that student-librarians as a result of self-efficacy always try to solve difficult problems on their own; can solve most problems if they put necessary effort; are confident in using different information resources, can easily utilize the library to get information for any assignment, it is easy for them to get current and accurate information, can easily handle whatever that comes their ways and can plan and organize themselves for any academic work among other things and there is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance of student-librarians. The findings of some other studies indicated positive relationship between academic self-efficacy and positive emotions (Sadi & Uyar, 2013; Villavicencio & Bernardo, 2013; Ferla, Valcke & Cai, 2009; Putwain, Sander & Larkin, 2013;. Doménech-Betoret, Abellán-Roselló & Gómez-Artiga, 2017).

Indeed, research concerning the effect of peer influence on academic achievement has had a long history (Haller and Butterworth 1960; McDill & Coleman 1965; Duncan et al. 1968; Davies & Kandel 1981; Ream & Rumberger 2008; Hasan & Bagde 2013). In *The Adolescent Society*, Coleman advances an important argument: there exists a subculture among adolescents distinct from adult culture, and as peers at the same age, adolescents are more likely to be influenced by each other. Moreover, the effect of peers on the student's achievement is even larger than that of teachers and the school (Coleman 1961). Coleman also believes that peer inputs, in which better

students are put into the group of students with disadvantages, is a major solution to school issues (Coleman 1988). In a scholarly debate about social capital and academic achievement published in *American Sociological Review*, the two sides both acknowledge the significant effect of peers on academic achievement (Morgan and Sorensen 1999; Carbonaro 1999). Rich (2009) even goes as far as to suggest that the only way parents can influence their children is to choose peers for them. Harris might be exaggerating, but his idea that peers are the important path of generational reproduction coincides with the Wisconsin School's emphasis on the effect of significant others.

On the other hand, scholars never stopped questioning the importance of peers. Specifically, after taking endogeneity into account, some scholars argue that the effect of peer social capital is weak, unstable, and even negligible (Foster 2006), or that it only holds under certain conditions (Zimmerman 2003; Stinebrickner and Stinebrickner 2006). Giordano's (2003) review of a large amount of literature concludes that the convergence of young people and their peers on multiple dimensions is mainly an endogenous effect due to homogeneity bias, whereas the effect of peer network takes a subordinate, secondary role. In other words, the effect is one of "birds of the same feather flock together," rather than one of "taking the behavior of the company." In this respect, if we are not careful about endogenous selection in socialization when talking about peer social capital, the conclusion could be pale regardless of its generalization.

It is pertinent to state that many peer groups can be a positive influence on their friends as well. In view of this, Hasan and Bagde (2013) divide the mechanism of influence of social influence on academic achievement into direct and indirect effects, but disagree on which effect is the major one. It is thought that intelligent students help their peers bring up their grades. Likewise, girls with good friends who are considered intelligent tend to do better in school. There definitely seems to be a pattern in the influence of studious students. With that is said, another common theme is similar aspirations. Students that want to excel academically tend to hang out with others with similar aspirations. In line with the above division, Cheng (2020), believes that a peer in the same major as the student can affect the latter both directly through providing study resources and support, and indirectly through influencing the student's value and behavior. But when the peer and the student are in different majors, it is possible that only the indirect effect is

at play, as the peer would not be able to directly provide study help or knowledge material to the student. Based on this consideration

According to a study published by the Williams Project (2011) on the Study of Economics in Higher Education, stronger students do have an impact on their peers and actually help improve the overall academic performance of the peer group. A large study done by (the Center for Research in Education, Diversity and Excellence (CREDE) (1999) suggested that peer groups can "exert extraordinary influence" during early adolescence on personal goals and school aspirations. A study by the Uzezi & Deya (2017) showed that there was a "significant difference between students that belong to peer group and those that do not belong to peer group on the academic achievement of chemistry. Experts do agree that peer groups can have an influence on academic performance. However, they don't agree on the extent and variables of that influence.

All said and done, there have been other studies on peer influence and academic achievement. However, these researches focus on identifying causal effects and rarely talk about internal mechanisms by which peer network influences academic achievement (Stinebrickner and Stinebrickner 2006; Sacerdote 2011; Hasan and Bagde 2013).

In the last decades, research has equivocally proven the importance of academic achievement drive also known as academic achievement motivation on the learning experience and outcome of students. For instance, motivated students tend to have a better learning process and outcome (Lepper, Corpus & Iyengar, 2005), higher self-esteem, more creative (Eisenberger & Shanock, 2003), improved psychological well-being and more self-regulated (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Holistically, good number of authors did assert that academic achievement motivation contributes positively in the academic performance of students (Gotfried, Marcoulides, Gotfried, Pliver & Oliver, 2007). Awan, Noureen and Naz (2011), are of the view that lack of academic achievement drive is a big hurdle in learning and pertinent cause in the deterioration of students' academic attainment as students who lack the academic achievement drive are not enthusiastic in their learning efforts; do not pay attention in class, are disorganized and do things haphazardly.

In their study on the achievement motivation as predictor of academic achievement among students Erhuvwu and Adeyemi (2019) discovered that achievement motivation significantly

predicts academic achievement of senior secondary school students. From the result, it is observed that achievement motivation proved to have a stronger relationship of students' academic achievement in mathematics. It was also seen that students' achievement motivation displayed significantly more perseverance and effort, achievement drive, as well as reported better social and motivational relationship with academic achievement. However, students' academic achievement drive may be partially mediated by other cognitive and non-cognitive factors that may affect academic achievement positively. These according to Tavani and Losh (2003) include, levels of students' internal characteristics – such as motivation and self-confidence revealing that students' academic achievement motivation was significantly linked to a drive to achieve and that when students' level of confidence and motivation are high, their expectations of academic success will like-wise be high.

On how examination anxiety correlates with academic achievement drive, studies explicated that examination anxiety has impact on university level students and results showed that high achievers had less examination anxiety. Literature support effect of examination anxiety and teachers evaluation practice on student's academic achievement. High anxiety reduces level of motivation and academic achievement (Hancock, 2001; Khalid and Hasan, 2009). Hembree (1998) noted that 30% of students suffer from examination anxiety noting that high examination anxiety is commonly associated with low self-esteem, poor reading and poor mathematics achievement, failing grades, disruptive classroom behaviors negative attitude towards school and unpleasant feeling of nervousness as well as dread that stem from intense fear of failure. Sena, Lowe and Lee (2007) found that students with higher test anxiety obtain lower marks in examination. Chapell, Blanding, Siverstein, Takashi, Newman, Gubi and Mccain (2005) discovered in their study a significant inverse relationship between examination anxiety and grade point average (GPA) among students. While in their study on Relationship between Examination Anxiety and Academic Achievement among University Students Khizar, Anwar and Khanum (2015), noted that no signification relation was executed between examination anxiety and academic achievements among university students therefore there was no relationship between examination anxiety and academic achievement which was attributed to favorable and better institution environment. All said and done, examination anxiety is an

uneasiness or apprehension experienced before, during or after examination as a result of concern, worry or fear of uncertainty.

On a collective note, pedagogic research has discovered that academic achievement drive; academic self-efficacy and value-expectancy are the most influencing factors on students' academic behavior (Linnenbrick & Pintrich, 2002) which are further influenced by how students experience success; confidence, enthusiasm and how theory and practice are tied together.

3.0. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The study applied descriptive survey research design and utilized the simple random sampling techniques to select 399 library and information science students in the following selected universities; Abia State University, Uturu, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Imo State University, Owerri, Madonna University, Okija, Michael Okpara University Of Agriculture, Umudike, University Of Benin, Benin City, University Of Calabar, Calabar and University of Ibadan, Ibadan, with each university providing 40 (10.02%) respondents except Madonna University, Okija that provided 39 (9.84%) respondents.

3.2. Instrument for Data collection

Data for this study were collected through four instruments validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundation and Administration, Abia State University, Uturu. These are:

Students' Academic Achievement Desire Scale (SAADS). This was designed in line with that of Aremu & Hammed (2002) Students' Academic Achievement Motivation (SAAM) which is 2nd inventory in University of Ibadan multi-dynamic inventories of Achievement Motivation. It consist of 20 items developed on a 4 point Likert scale and validated through a pilot study by the researcher with a Cronbach Alpha of 0.72 and reliability coefficient using Guttman split half $r=0.84$.

Academic Self-efficacy Scale (ASS). The students' academic self-efficacy was measured using an adopted and modified version of the Morgan-Links student academic self-efficacy scale

developed by Morgan and Links (1999). The used instrument contained 30 items validated through a pilot study while test-retest method was used to establish the external reliability of the instrument which stood at 0.70 and the internal consistency was measured using Cronbach Alpha and the result was 0.80. The original instrument is a-30 item scale that had a total reliability coefficient of 0.82 while the response format range from 'really agree-1 to really disagree-4'

Examination Anxiety Scale (EAS). The respondents' examination anxiety was measured using Sokan Examination Anxiety Scale (SEAS). The scale is an 18-item instrument that measures examination anxiety with statements that pertain to ones feelings towards examination. The SEAS adopts a true or false response pattern with true response scoring-1 and false scoring-0. The obtained score was calculated in percentage. For instance a score of 18 is 100%. This implies that fractions of 18 were converted to percentage. A high index of score suggests anxiety disorder whereas a low index is seen as otherwise. The reliability coefficient of the scale is 0.725 and the half split 0.682 (Sokan, 1998)

Peer Influence Scale (PIS). The peer influence scale instrument constructed by Adeyamo & Torubeli (2008) was used to measure the peer influence. It is an instrument with 12-items with response format ranging from 'not at all like me' to 'very much like me'. It has an overall reliability index of 0.78.

3.3. Administration of Instrument

The researcher obtained consent letters from the heads of the various Library and Information Science department of the studied universities and after which with the help of some selected lecturers in the department, the essence of the study was explained to them, thereafter, the instruments were administered to them and subsequently collected with the help of the lecturers on completion.

3.4. Method for Data Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at $P > 0.05$ level of significance.

4.0. Data Presentation and Analysis

As the intent of this study is to ascertain the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, data collected for this study were purely analyzed using the PPMC with the summarized data presented in four tables according to the research objectives, questions and formulated hypotheses.

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment correlation (PPMC) analysis showing the correlation between Academic Self-efficacy and Academic Achievement Drive

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R	DF	P
Academic achievement drive	399	3.20	8.14	0.545	.396	Sig. 0.05
Academic self-efficacy	399	31.26	6.49			

The analyzed data as summarized in table 1 above reveal that there is a statistical significant correlation between academic self-efficacy drive and library and information science students' academic achievement drive (under DF 0.396 R=0.546, $p < 0.05$) with a mean of 8,14 and 6.49 respectively. This result implies that library and information science students' academic self-efficacy impacts positively on their academic achievement drive. It was this ground, that H01 which states that there is no statistical significant relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic achievement motivation of library and information science students was rejected thereby answering research question one.

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment correlation (PPMC) analysis showing the correlation between peer influence and Academic Achievement Drive

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R	DF	P
Achievement Drive	399	30.20	8.14	0.334	.386	Sig 0.05
Peer Influence	399	33.93	4.30			

Table 2 is the analyzed data in respect of research question two and H02 which are on the relationship between peer influence and library and information science academic achievement drive. The data show a positive correlation between peer influence and academic achievement drive of library and information science students R (0.386) =334, $p < 0.05$) with peer influence mean and standard deviation as 33.93 and 2.30 respectively. The implication is that peer influence could positively or negatively impact on the academic achievement drive of library and information science students. It is with outcome that the HO2: 'There is no statistical significant relationship between peer influence and academic achievement drive of library and information science students' was rejected and answer to research question two provided

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Product Moment correlation (PPMC) analysis showing the correlation between Examination Anxiety and Academic Achievement Drive

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R	DF	P
Academic Achievement Drive	399	30.19	8.14	0.367	.396	Sig 0.05
Examination Anxiety	399	33.35	4.84			

The data in table 3 show the relationship between examination anxiety and academic achievement drive of library and information science students. The analyzed data indicate that there is a significant relationship between library and information science students' level of examination anxiety and their academic achievement drive at $R(0.396) = 0.367$). With this result the H03: 'There is no statistical significant relationship between examination anxiety and academic achievement drive of library and information science students', is hereby rejected as examination anxiety can impair the academic achievement drive of library and information science students. To this end, the answer to research question three has been provided.

Table: 4: Descriptive Statistics and correlation matrix of relationship between the variables (academic achievement drive, academic self-efficacy, examination anxiety and peer influence)

Variables	N	Mean	Std Dev	R	1	2	3	4
Academic Achievement Drive	399	30.20	8.14	0.545	1.000			
Academic Self-efficacy	399	31.26	6.50	0.366	.	1.000		
Examination anxiety	399	33.35	4.84	0.350			1.000	
Peer influence	399	33.94	4.29	0.335				1.000

Based on the data collected and expressed in this descriptive statistics and correlation matrix of relationship between the variables which highlight the mean, standard deviation and zero order correlation among the variables as displayed in the table 4 above in the observation was that, there exist a significant relationship between the independent variables (Academic self-efficacy, Peer influence and Examination anxiety) and dependent variable (Academic achievement drive) in the following order of magnitude; academic achievement drive ($R=0.545$, $p<0.05$); academic self-efficacy ($R=0.388$, $p<0.05$); Examination anxiety ($R=0.350$, $p<0.05$) and Peer influence (0.335 , $p<0.05$). The implication is that is that there is a positive correlation between Academic self-efficacy, examination anxiety as well as peer influence (the independent variables) and the dependent variable (academic achievement drive) of library and information science students.

5.0. Discussion of Results

The outcome of this study in the first instance shows that there is a statistical relationship between academic self-efficacy of library and information science students and their academic achievement drive (see table 1). This implies that library and information science students' self-confident and the belief that they can excel academically could be positive academic motivational factors. This finding is in conformity with the finding of Alyami et al. (2017) who conducted a study on 214 university students and revealed that academic self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on their academic performance as well as the assertion of Bandura (1995) and Adeyemo (2007) that the sources of information from which students appraise their academic self-efficacy beliefs are performance accomplishment, their vicarious experience, and persuasion they get from others and their psychological arousal. He further argued that when students have strong beliefs in their capabilities to undertake academic tasks, they set comparable goal and necessary machinery in motion for actualizing their goals.

The study also discovered that there was a positive correlation between peer influence and academic achievement drive of library and information science students $R(0.386) = 334, p < 0.05$ with peer influence mean and standard deviation as 33.93 and 2.30 respectively. The implication is that peer influence could positively or negatively impact on the academic achievement drive of library and information science students. This discovering is in agreement with Cheng (2020), believes that a peer in the same major as the student can affect the latter both directly through providing study resources and support, and indirectly through influencing the student's value and behavior. But when the peer and the student are in different majors, it is possible that only the indirect effect is at play, as the peer would not be able to directly provide study help or knowledge material to the

The outcome of this study further revealed that there is a correlation between examination anxiety and academic achievement drive of library and information science students. The analyzed data indicate that there is a significant relationship between library and information science students' level of examination anxiety and their academic achievement drive at $R(0.396) = 0.367$). However this finding is contrary to that of Asma Khizar and Muhammad Nadeem Anwar (2020) who in their study on the relationship between examination anxiety and academic achievement

among University Students revealed that there is no relationship between examination anxiety and students academic achievement. It was found that examination anxiety is not caused of low, average and high achievement of the student as teacher, parents and educational administrator were playing effective role to manage examination anxiety of the students.

On the other hand, the outcome affirms studies explicated that examination anxiety has impact on university level students and results showed that high achievers had less examination anxiety. Literature support effect of examination anxiety and teachers evaluation practice on student's academic achievement. High anxiety reduces level of motivation and academic achievement (Hancock, 2001; Khalid and Hasan, 2009). Hembree (1998) noted that 30% of students suffer from examination anxiety noting that high examination anxiety is commonly associated with low self-esteem, poor reading and poor mathematics achievement, failing grades, disruptive classroom behaviors negative attitude towards school and unpleasant feeling of nervousness as well as dread that stem from intense fear of failure. Sena, Lowe and Lee (2007) found that students with higher test anxiety obtain lower marks in examination. Chapell, Blanding, Siverstein, Takashi, Newman, Gubi and Mccain (2005) discovered in their study a significant inverse relationship between examination anxiety and grade point average (GPA) among students.

Finally, the study found that there exist a significant relationship between the independent variables (Academic self-efficacy, Peer influence and Examination anxiety) and dependent variable (Academic achievement drive) in the following order of magnitude; academic achievement drive ($R=0.545$, $p<0.05$); academic self-efficacy ($R=0.388$, $p<0.05$); Examination anxiety ($R=0.350$, $p<0.05$) and Peer influence (0.335 , $p<0.05$). The implication is that is that there is a positive correlation between Academic self-efficacy, examination anxiety as well as peer influence (the independent variables) and the dependent variable (academic achievement drive) of library and information science students. This finding therefore corroborate the pedagogic research that discovered that academic achievement drive; academic self-efficacy and value-expectancy are the most influencing factors on students' academic behavior (Linnenbrick & Pintrich, 2002) which are further influenced by how students experience success, confidence, enthusiasm and how theory and practice are tied together.

5.1. Conclusion and Recommendations

The result of this study did establish one fact which is that the independent variables (academic self-efficacy, peer influence and examination anxiety) are correlates of the dependent variable (academic achievement drive). Imperatively, they act as catalyst towards students' intellectual functioning and academic attainment. In the area of peer influence, it should be perceived from the positive angle and students encouraged towards that direction. The deduction therefore is that library and information science students and by extension students generally, who exhibit low academic achievement drive is bound to experience high levels of examination anxiety, exhibit poor confidence (low academic self-efficacy), anti-social behavior and be ill-driven to achieve academically. This development left them to down-syndrome which irks them to seeing themselves as academic failures as such often develop syndrome that includes a variety of self-defeating motives that may serve as bottleneck and prevent them from attaining academic excellence in school. This situation more often than not has compounding and devastating effect on the academic and intellectual well-being of ill-driven student-librarians. In fact when students are not self-efficacious, anxious and negatively influenced by peers, they could be ill-motivated to achieve in their academic learning task as a result of impaired academic achievement drive to excel. The point being made is that for purposeful learning, library and information science students need to be put in the right frame of mind through the enhancement of their academic achievement drive as to impact positively on their intellectual functioning and academic attainment as totality of it, will lead to effective learning. In the light of the above and the outcome of this study, the followed recommendations are proffered.

- Charity they say begins at home, to this end, the act of building self-confidence in the students should start from home. It behooves parents to make their children discover who they are; their capability and why they should have self-concept and confidence and to the lecturers and other stakeholders to serve as mentors and role models to look onto by the students. As teachers, lecturers should encourage students from the start to set academic goals and encourage them into realizing same through close monitoring and developing their ability skills through advise.
- There is need for universities in developing countries to replicate what is obtained in other universities of developed nations like; United States, UK, Germany and Canada

where there are well established units for students' counseling with qualified staff as well as academic advisors who are assigned to individual students as academic attainment goals watchdogs. The implication is that academic achievement motivation should be enhanced using appropriate counseling strategies.

- Their assumption that examination anxiety is a common academic process phenomenon is not in doubt but what should be questioned is the viability. Lecturers and other stakeholders involved in the training of students should make them realize that examinations/tests are not a do or die affair rather normal academic processes which only act as means to an end and not an end itself. A situation whereby lecturers threaten students with failure and demanding gratifications (in the form of sex in the case of female students and money in the case of male students) should be treated as a serious anti-social behavior that should not be swept under the carpet. As this single act, has contributed in no small measure in hiking examination anxiety among students.
- As a follow up to the above, lecturers and university administrators should play effective role in managing students' examination anxiety by ensuring that examinations and test are not conducted under fire brigade approach. Students should be given enough time to prepare for examinations and should be conducted under a conducive and serene environment.
- The global axiom is that 'No man is an island' and in librarianship the parlance is that 'No library is self-sufficient' therefore, no student can operate in isolation. The emphasis is that students should be oriented by both parents and university administrators on the type of friends to keep considering the fact that peer influence may be two-ways; negative or positive.
- To whom much is given, much is expected. The whole effort being made is to enhance students' intellectual functioning so as to attain the desired academic standard. On the part of the students, they should have at the back of their minds in the cause of their academic pursuance the purpose for being in the university. The key aim is to learn, therefore, they should as a matter of necessity take their studies seriously. Regular and effective use of the library should be paramount as to realizing their academic achievement dream. Students should believe in their ability to excel, should as a matter of necessity take their studies seriously, form good study habit and set for themselves

SMART goals that can spur them into developing positive academic achievement drive for academic excellence.

- Heads of department of library and information science should start doing the needful. A situation whereby heads of department see themselves as mere boss and not fathers/mothers of students is not in the best interest of students' academic well-being. They should develop listening ears as to knowing students' academic challenges instead of scaring them away with their snobby and bossy attitude. Heads from the on-set (from orientation) should start the awareness campaign of 'know yourselves and the purpose for which you are in the university as students' and regularly organize talks with the students as a way of giving them sense of belonging thus enhancing their academic achievement drive.
- Finally, government on her part, should make learning attractive for the students by providing for the universities basic amenities such as functional libraries, conducive lecture halls, regular power supply well furnished hostels among others.

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